

MEDICAL SCIENCES

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF PSYCHOTHERAPY TREATMENT FOR SOMATOFORM DISORDERS IN CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS

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Abstract

Somatoform disorders involve physical symptoms without a clear medical cause, often leading to significant distress. Effective treatment frequently includes psychotherapy, which aims to address the psychological aspects of these disorders. Cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT) and other therapeutic methods can help patients manage symptoms, reduce distress, and improve overall functioning. This abstract highlights the role of psychotherapy in the treatment of somatoform disorders and its impact on enhancing patient outcomes.

Keywords: somatoform disorders, treatment, psychotherapy

Introduction. Somatoform disorders, also known as somatic symptom and related disorders (SSRDs) in the DSM-5, are defined by the presence of physical symptoms that do not have a clear medical explanation. These diseases frequently cause severe discomfort and incapacity in children and adolescents, jeopardizing their social, academic, and family lives. This study investigates the efficacy of psychotherapeutic therapies, particularly cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT), family therapy, and psychodynamic approaches, in treating SSRDs in young patients.

Diagnosing somatoform disorders in children and adolescents is challenging due to their developmental stage and the overlap of physical and psychological symptoms. These disorders often co-occur with anxiety, depression, and other mental health issues, complicating the diagnosis. Accurate identification usually requires a multidisciplinary team, including doctors, psychiatrists, psychologists, and sometimes school officials, to evaluate the child's psychological, physiological, and social factors. Common subtypes include Somatic Symptom Disorder (SSD), which involves distressing bodily symptoms and excessive thoughts or behaviors related to those symptoms. SSRDs are fairly common in youth, with 10-15% reporting somatic symptoms at times, and a diagnosable prevalence of 4-6%. They are more frequent in girls, particularly during stressful transitions like puberty. Risk factors include a family history of anxiety, depression, or somatoform disorders, trauma, and environmental stressors such as bullying or family conflict. (Schulte, 2011).

Psychological trauma significantly influences the development of somatoform disorders, with traumatic events or chronic stressors potentially causing lasting

physical symptoms in children and teens. Traits like emotional instability and anxiety increase the risk of somatic symptoms, complicating diagnosis and treatment. Neurosis, a response to trauma, can lead to chronic medical issues that affect both psychological and physical aspects.

Modern psychiatric literature highlights the pathogenic nature of uncertain or difficult decisions, where unavoidable distress can cause frustration. Examples include incompatible work demands or ongoing family conflicts.

Excessive internet use, a growing issue, has been linked to increased psychological distress and somatic symptoms in teens, including problems with attention, sleep, and emotional regulation. Research suggests that internet addiction can exacerbate these issues, particularly in those with pre-existing mental health problems. There is debate over whether these issues are caused by internet use itself or by existing disorders. Teens often face challenges with reality and norms, and without parental oversight, unrestricted internet access can lead to negative behaviors and addictions, mirroring the patterns seen in their parents and peers.

Recent research indicates that screen addiction may be hereditary, linked to 5-HTTLPR gene polymorphisms and DRD2 gene mutations. Similar genetic and brain structural abnormalities are found in addiction to substances like nicotine and cocaine. Data from 2016 show that internet addiction leads to reduced cortical thickness, particularly in the orbitofrontal cortex, decreased gray matter volume, immature white matter, and dysfunction in brain areas like the insula and right amygdala. These brain changes impact behavior control, attention, and emotional regulation, correlating

with the amount of time spent online, and contribute to poorer cognitive impulse control.

Cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT) has emerged as a highly effective treatment for somatic symptom and related disorders (SSRDs), targeting cognitive distortions and emotional responses that exacerbate physical complaints. In addition to CBT, family therapy and psychodynamic approaches are useful when family dynamics or past traumas contribute to persistent symptoms. SSRDs impose significant costs on healthcare systems and are major causes of disability, making it crucial to understand the psychological factors that influence these disorders. Evaluating the severity of medically unexplained symptoms—such as their impact on daily life and healthcare use—is essential for refining diagnosis and treatment strategies (Ricarda Mewes, 2022).

In 2013, the American Psychiatric Association (APA) introduced somatic symptom disorder (SSD) in the DSM-5, replacing previous diagnoses like somatization disorder. SSD has three key diagnostic criteria: (A) the presence of one or more painful or disabling somatic symptoms, (B) disproportionate and persistent thoughts about the symptoms, high anxiety regarding health, or excessive time and energy devoted to health concerns, and (C) symptoms lasting more than six months. This update reflects a new understanding of these complex conditions and aims to improve diagnosis and treatment (Löwe B, 2022).

Patients with potential somatic symptom disorder (SSD) are often referred to mental health care facilities and psychosomatic or psychiatric consultation services. Self-report questionnaires like the Patient Health Questionnaire-15 (PHQ-15) and the Whiteley Index aid in screening and diagnosis. For patients with persistent physical symptoms, consider SSD early, avoid (Henningens P.2018) unnecessary investigations, and pay attention to indications of both physical and emotional distress. Evaluate the patient's experiences, expectations, functioning, and check for additional symptoms, anxiety, substance use, and suicidal thoughts. If SSD is diagnosed, classify it as mild, moderate, or severe based on symptom criteria.

Effective SSD management involves a stepped care approach, integrating primary care, somatic specialists, and mental health professionals within a biopsychosocial model. SSD is categorized as mild if one psycho-behavioral symptom is present, moderate if two or more symptoms are present, and severe if multiple symptoms or one very severe symptom is noted.

Recent studies, including those by Löwe et al. (2022) and Zou et al., have advanced our understanding

of SSD. Löwe et al. (2022) confirmed the reliability of SSD diagnoses but called for more specific psychological criteria. Zou et al. found infrared thermography (IRT) to be a useful tool for diagnosing persistent somatoform pain disorder (PSPD), offering valuable insights despite its limitations. These studies highlight the importance of a thorough diagnostic approach for improving SSD diagnosis and treatment (Milton Anguyo, 2024).

Despite various approaches to managing childhood neuroses, doctors in this field (including neurologists, psychologists, and psychiatrists) agree that, in all cases, a collaborative effort among parents, doctors, and educators is required for the timely detection of psychological disorders in children and the treatment of their underlying causes.

Finally, psychotherapy, particularly CBT, has shown promise in treating the symptoms of somatoform disorders in children and adolescents. However, further research is needed to improve these therapy procedures and look into long-term outcomes. A multidisciplinary approach involving mental health professionals, medical specialists, and educators is critical for ensuring quick diagnosis and comprehensive treatment.

Research materials and methods.

Between 2022 and 2024, the study investigated 100 individuals aged 2 to 18 (59 males and 41 girls) with diverse somatoform diseases. The majority (65 youngsters) were Tbilisi residents, with the remainder 35 from various parts of Georgia. All patients were evaluated in the Academic Clinic of Pediatric Medicine at Tbilisi State Medical University and the Psychotherapeutic Gestalt Clinic.

The qualitative variables presented as the absolute and percentage values. The difference between the variables in the groups was determined by Chi Square test; the difference. The results were considered significant if $p < 0.05$. Statistical test were performed using the software package - SPSS-23.

The study classified somatoform disorders into the following clinical features: tic hyperkinesia (14), speech disorders (24), attention deficit and hyperactivity disorder (7), mixed behavioral and emotional disorders (38), sleep disorders (34), day and night enuresis (8), screen addiction syndrome (14), and chronic somatoform autonomic and vegetative dysfunction (15) (Table N1).

Mixed behavioral and emotional disorders and sleep disorders were distinguished by the highest frequency, attention deficit and hyperactivity disorder and day and night enuresis were the rarest.

Table1.

Factors	I group (31)		II group (34)		III group (23)		IVgroup (12)		χ^2	p
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%		
Tic Hyperkinesia	2	6.45	8	24.24	2	8.70	2	20.00	4.64	0.2002
Speech Disorder	17	54.84	4	12.12	2	8.70	1	10.00	23.52	0.00003143
Attention Deficit and Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD)	0	0.00	3	9.09	2	8.70	2	20.00	4.331	0.2279
Mixed Behavioral and Emotional Disorder	18	58.06	12	36.36	4	17.39	4	40.00	9.66	0.02169
Sleep Disorder	16	51.61	6	18.18	5	21.74	7	70.00	13.04	0.004541
Daytime and Nighttime Enuresis	0	0.00	2	6.06	5	21.74	1	10.00	8.803	0.03202
Screen Addiction Syndrome	0	0.00	1	3.03	5	21.74	8	80.00	45.05	<0.0000001
Chronic Somatoform Autonomic, Vegetative Dysfunction	0	0.00	0	0.00	8	34.78	7	70.00	41.55	<0.0000001

To rule out organic damage, all patients underwent general blood and urine testing, along with glucose, TSH, FT4, rheumatic activity measurements, ECG, and echocardiography. The physicians conducted EEG and polysomnography if needed. Ophthalmologist, pediatricians, and cardio-rheumatologists provided consultations. Eight patients needed psychiatric consultations, and two genetic consultations. All 100 patients had a psychological consultation and neurological examination.

Neuropsychological research evaluated both verbal and nonverbal cognitive functions, including communication, memory, and perceptual abilities. Motor functions like strength and coordination were also assessed using the Luria test and visual-motor skills test (VMI). Results showed 60% of children had significant

deficits in fine motor skills, though auditory and visual gnosis were normal. The patients expressed difficulties with rhythm imitation and impulse control.

The study found neuropsychological symptoms in children with somatoform disorders, tic hyperkinesia, stuttering, and screen addiction, though some symptoms were minimal. The "Incomplete Sentences" method assessed behavioral and emotional status, revealing attitudes toward various aspects of their lives through clinical analysis. Statistical processing was not performed.

The findings showed negative impacts among patients with conversion disorders, phobias, stuttering, nocturnal enuresis, daytime encopresis, and computer

game dependency on their relationships and self-esteem. Most felt guilty and reported being treated "badly" by their families, with fears of punishment, abandonment, and not be loved. Despite those stresses, they remained hopeful and valued their peers.

The study found that psychologists and, if necessary, speech therapists are more effective for treating somatoform disorders than drug treatment alone. Cognitive behavioral therapy, focusing on emotional states and harmful habits, proved especially beneficial. Active parental involvement and lifestyle changes were crucial for long-term effects, particularly in screen addiction cases.

Twenty-four patients had speech difficulties. In 12 stuttering cases, speech therapy alone was ineffective; however, combining cognitive behavioral and gestalt

therapies led to significant improvements, with stuttering fully resolved in eight cases. Psychotherapy was also effective for managing tic hyperkinesis, ADHD, mixed behavioral and emotional problems, sleep disturbances, screen addiction, and chronic somatoform autonomic dysfunction. Day and night enuresis showed the least improvement, with only one patient benefiting.

Group I did not have ADHD, enuresis, screen addiction syndrome, or chronic somatoform autonomic dysfunction, which were only found in Groups III and IV. Speech disorders and mixed behavioral and emotional issues were more common in Group I, while sleep disorders, screen addiction syndrome, and chronic somatoform autonomic dysfunction were more prevalent in Group IV.

Conclusions. The results of the studies carried out can be....

Several major discoveries came from our intensive examination of 100 people aged 2 to 18 suffering from diverse somatoform diseases. The study included a varied sample, with participants from both urban and rural areas of Georgia. Clinical characteristics were diverse, with mixed behavioral and emotional abnormalities, sleep disturbances, and speech disorders being the most common. Neuropsychological tests revealed that many children had significant deficiencies in fine motor skills and impulse control. These findings were validated by both verbal and nonverbal cognitive examinations, which highlighted difficulties in rhythm imitation and fine visual analysis. Despite these problems, the auditory and visual gnosis were mostly within normal limits. The "Incomplete Sentences" technique gave new information on the diseases' emotional and cognitive dimensions. It demonstrated a poor influence on patients' relationships with their parents and teachers, as well as an overwhelming sense of shame and terror. These emotional responses were frequently marked by fears of retribution, desertion, and unfulfilled emotional demands, despite an underlying sense of hope for the future.

The research findings show that integrated psychotherapy techniques, such as cognitive behavioral therapy and gestalt therapy, are more successful than medicine alone in treating somatoform disorders. For diseases such as stuttering, tic hyperkinesia, and screen

addiction, combining psychotherapy with particular therapies customized to each problem resulted in considerable improvements. Active parental involvement and lifestyle changes were critical to ensuring long-term success, particularly in situations of screen addiction.

Overall, our findings highlight the significance of a multimodal treatment approach that addresses both the psychological and affective aspects of somatoform disorders. This method not only improves symptom management, but it also promotes greater emotional well being and interpersonal relationships in affected children and adolescents.

The study limitation: the study did not focus on longitudinal effect of psychotherapy. After finishing the psychotherapy the gained skills is effective in children or adolescents or the symptoms main return after several months or years.

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